

Effect of Arginine Supplementation on Broiler Performance

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Abstract

In this fast and rapidly growing poultry industry, it plays significant role in meat production, food security, employment opportunities, and economic growth. Dietary Arginine in chicks is used for the synthesis of protein and as a precursor of metabolically important molecules, e.g., nitric oxide (NO), glutamate, polyamines, and proline (Wu *et al.*, 2009). Arginine shows various functions like vasodilation, energy for muscle contraction, immune response, cell growth and proliferation, free radical scavengers, reduced apoptosis and wound healing (Miri *et al.*, 2022). Chicken lacks the enzyme mitochondrial carbamoyl phosphate synthase I (CPS-I), crucial for the urea cycle and has lower activity of ornithine transcarboxylase (OTC) making it dietary essential (Tamir & Ratner, 1963). Arginine shows physiological functions like wound healing, immune function, hormone secretion, vascular tone, insulin sensitivity, and endothelial function (Tong & Barbul., 2004). Arginine increases protein synthesis through GH and insulin secretion stimulates IGF-1 Secretion. Nitric oxide inhibits the lipogenesis Pathway & stimulates lipolysis, decreases fatty acid synthesis and decreases body fat deposition (Shi *et al.*, 2006). In the gut, arginine mediates the trophic effects on mitosis in the intestinal region to subsequently enhance villus size and number. Arginine changes in the intestinal microbiota & reduce alpha diversity. It increases the weight of lymphoid organs (spleen, thymus, bursa of Fabricius) and affects immunomodulation by promoting a response from lymphocytes to mitogens (Gao *et al.*, 2017). Arginine protects against necrotic enteritis, IBD, and coccidiosis by promoting gut integrity & immune response. Arginine improves growth performance, immune system, carcass weight and gut health at various levels of arginine supplements above the NRC recommendation.

Keyword: urea cycle, gut health, immune response, disease prevention

Introduction

The poultry industry in India is one of the fastest-growing agricultural sub-sectors, contributing significantly to the country's food security, employment opportunities, and economic growth. In this fast-growing world poultry industry development is achieved by

giving high-quality proteins & balanced amino acids in diets which are pivotal for rapid growth & efficient protein deposition. Which helps in Enhancing muscle growth, and body tissue synthesis, and facilitating key metabolic and growth processes (Beski *et al.*, 2015). To meet this protein requirement, formulate a poultry diet with specific amino acids that enhance

growth rate, FCR and reproductive performance (Kidd *et al.*, 2021). In these diversified amino acids, Arginine is our key component that helps to enhance growth, energy metabolism, immune response, and wound healing. In 1886, Swiss chemist **Ernst Schulze** first isolated the amino acid **arginine** from a lupin seedling extract.

Why dietary supplementation of arginine is required for broiler???

Unlike mammals, which synthesize urea as nitrogen waste and during the urea cycle, arginine serves as an intermediate product that fulfills the arginine requirement in mammals. But poultry synthesize uric acid as nitrogen waste, so arginine is not derived as an intermediate product and poultry needs to dietary supplementation of arginine.

The Arginine de novo synthesis is highly dependent on the concentration and activity of the key enzymes such as carbamoyl phosphate synthase I (CPS-I), ornithine transcarboxylase (OTC), arginosuccinate synthetase (ASS), and arginosuccinate lyase (ASL).

Tamir and Ratner proved that chickens lack carbamoyl phosphate synthase I, which would catalyze ammonia fixation, and have a scarcely active ornithine transcarboxylase that transfers the fixed nitrogen to ornithine to generate citrulline, an indispensable intermediate for the urea cycle.

Poultry cannot synthesize Arg de novo from ornithine and ammonia. Furthermore, these authors also detected low activities of ASS and ASL in the spleen, kidney, pancreas, and intestinal tract. L-citrulline can be converted, to a limited extent, to Arg in the macrophage of birds, serving as a precursor of nitric oxide (NO). However, this sparing effect

of citrulline over arginine is not enough to fulfil the arginine need in a growing bird. Therefore, poultry is highly dependent on arginine's dietary supply.

While dietary citrulline can be converted to arginine in chicken macrophages and kidneys, facilitating nitric oxide production, this pathway's limited activity in essential organs does not satisfy the complete arginine requirements for growth.

Importance of arginine

Arginine processes various hormones, including growth hormone, prolactin, insulin, and catecholamines (Brugaletta *et al.*, 2023). Arginine is the precursor of metabolically important molecules, e.g., nitric oxide (NO), glutamate, polyamines, and proline (Wu *et al.*, 2009). For poultry raised at high altitudes suffering from heart disease and subsequent ascites syndrome arginine supplementation leads to increased nitric oxide production and helps them to regulate vasodilation (Miri *et al.*, 2022). In the starter phase, chicks require an acute need for arginine supplements because of immune system development and early microbial challenges (Corzo and Kidd, 2003).

Arginine reduces intestinal permeability and the healing of the ulcers that occur in the digestive tract. It also increases the jejunal activities for carbohydrate and protein digestion (Uni and Ferket, 2003).

The **higher requirement** of arginine in commercial broilers may be due to the **higher rate of protein deposition for quicker growth, less synthesis of endogenous arginine and antagonistic metabolic interaction between arginine and lysine** (Castro *et al.*, 2019; Khajali & Wideman, 2010).

Arginine increases insulin production, glucose production and lipid metabolism because it is involved in the production of a variety of enzymes and hormones. (Balch *et al.*, 1997). Arginine shows various physiological roles in the body including immune function, Vasodilator, Wound healing, Hormone secretion, Nitrogen balance, Insulin sensitivity, Cell division, Antioxidant and T-cell proliferation (Tong, B. C & Barbul A, 2004).

The National Research Council (NRC) requirement of arginine for broilers is **1.25%, 1.10%, and 1.00%** of the diet for up to **3 weeks, 3–6 weeks, and 6–8 weeks** of age, respectively (National Research Council, 1994).

Metabolism of arginine

Metabolism of arginine is a complex process and it occurs through and occurs through various enzymatic reactions. The key enzymes involved in arginine catabolism are 1. Nitric Oxide Synthase (NOS), 2. Arginase 3. arginine decarboxylase (ADC) and 4. arginine: glycine amino amidinotransferase (AGAT).

In this process, Glycine receives an amidino group from arginine in a reaction catalyzed by the enzyme L-Arg: Gly aminotransferase (AGAT) mainly in the kidney, Guanidino acetic acid (GAA) is produced. GAA is then transported to the liver where it is methylated by S-adenosyl methionine (SAM) in a reaction

catalysed by the enzyme guanidinoacetate N-methyltransferase to form Creatine. This Creatine is transported from the liver to the cells with high energetic requirements such as skeletal muscles, the heart and brain. Nitric Oxide Synthase (NOS) cleaved the arginine into nitric oxide and citrulline is derived as a byproduct. Nitric oxide shows a variety of functions like vasodilation, spermatogenesis, embryogenesis and immune response.

Arginine is cleaved by the enzyme arginase to form urea and ornithine. The reaction can be represented by the following equation: **Arginine + H₂O = Ornithine + urea**

Ornithine can be directly converted to proline by the enzyme ornithine cyclo-deaminase. This proline effects on cell proliferation, cell repair, wound healing and free radical scavengers. The enzyme ornithine aminotransferase catalyzes the transfer of the amino group from ornithine to α -ketoglutarate, producing glutamate-5-semialdehyde, which can be further converted into glutamate which activates glutamate synthetase enzyme which causes scavenging of reactive oxygen species (ROS). L-arginine is converted into agmatine through a decarboxylation reaction catalyzed by the enzyme arginine decarboxylase (ADC) which shows an Anti-proliferative & anti-inflammatory effect. Agmatine is then further metabolized into polyamines, such as putrescine, through the action of agmatinase which serves important functions in modulating gene expression, cell growth and proliferation, protein translation, antioxidant & reduced apoptosis.

Ornithine is decarboxylated by ornithine decarboxylase (ODC) to form putrescine, which is the precursor for polyamines such as spermidine and spermine.

L-arginine →
Ornithine → Putrescine → Spermidine → Spermi

ne

Arginine Sparing effect

The **arginine sparing effect** refers to the phenomenon where the presence of certain compounds in the diet can reduce the requirement for arginine by sparing it from being used in specific metabolic pathways.

1. **Citrulline:** Bypass hepatic metabolism, heat labile, Secretion of inflammatory cytokines, not authorized as a feed additive
2. **GAA:** Immediate precursor of creatine, highly thermostable and high recovery rate use as a feed additive, Approved by EU commission and US-FDA
3. **Creatin:** Energy supply in skeletal muscle, Thermal instability, promotes muscle, Protein synthesis, Creatine also has anti-apoptotic and anti-oxidative effects on cells, not utilized as a feed additive

(McBreairty *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2019)

Role of Arginine

A. Increase protein synthesis

Arginine suppresses the somatostatin hormone from pancreas and increases release

of GH from anterior pituitary gland & When glucose level is rise arginine stimulate b cell of Langerhans and release insulin. Both GH & insulin both show synergistic effect and release insulin like growth factor (IGF-1). Arginine also increases the concentration of creatine which causes the up-regulation of IGF-1 genes and ultimately stimulates the IGF-1 production. This insulin-like growth factor (IGF-1) causes Reducing protein breakdown & stimulates protein synthesis. Arginine also causes production of polyamines which cause RNA and DNA synthesis and ultimately lead to

A	Increase protein synthesis
B	Reduce abdomen fat
C	Gut health
D	Immune function
E	Disease prevention

protein synthesis and cell proliferation.

B. Reduce abdomen fat

Modern strains of broilers contain **15% to 20% fat** in which **85%** of this fat is not physiologically required for body function (Choct *et al.*, 2000). Excessive accumulation of abdominal fat in the broiler industry plays a significant impact as it leads to wastage of dietary energy with \$2.7 billion economic loss annually, reduces carcass yield, and negatively impacts consumer preference (Wen *et al.*, 2019).

Estimation of lipogenic enzymes in other tissues such as adipose tissue can also reveal the level of fatty acid synthesis and fat accumulation in the body (Jobgen *et al.*, 2009) demonstrated that dietary supplementation of L-Arg was effective in **increasing muscle compared to fat** in avian species. Arginine decreases FAS gene activity in the liver resulting in decreased fatty acids synthesis and storage of triglycerides in the body & Increased expression of carnitine palmitoyl transferase I (CPT-I) which is involved in β -oxidation of FA resulting in decreased fat accumulation (Found *et al.*, 2013).

Arginine increases nitric oxide production, which is a potent vasodilator that dilates the blood vessels and increases the flow of blood in the heart. It inhibits lipogenesis (conversion of CHO to fat) pathway and stimulates lipolysis in adipose tissue so ultimately results in decrease fatty acid synthesis and decrease body fat deposition (Shi *et al.*, 2006).

C. Gut health

Arginine increases the concentration of polyamines which are responsible for cellular proliferation, migration and apoptosis in the intestine and the development of intestine in the early life of chicks (Murakami *et al.*, 2012). Arginine mediates the trophic effects on mitosis in the intestinal region to subsequently enhance villus size and number (Uni *et al.*, 1998). Changes in the intestinal microbiota, such as reduced alpha diversity and relative abundance of Firmicutes and Proteobacteria, as well as increased abundance of Bacteroidetes and Lactobacillus salivarius. These changes can potentially improve intestinal conditions and contribute to improved growth performance (Brugaletta *et al.*, 2023).

D. Immune response

- Increasing production of nitric oxide and this destroys pathogenic micro-organisms

- Increase antibody titer against NDV
- Increasing weight of lymphoid organs (spleen, thymus, bursa of fabricius)
- Immune-boosting and its inflammation relieving property
- Affects immunomodulation by promoting response from lymphocyte to mitogens such as phytohemagglutinin and Concanavalin A

Macrophage polarization can be categorized into M1 and M2 macrophages based on arginine metabolism (Lumeng *et al.*, 2007). Activation of M1 macrophages by microbial products such as LPS, Th1 cytokines such as IL-1 β , IFN- γ , or TNF- α , recruits macrophages to the M1 pathway and induces the expression of the NOS gene. M1 macrophage possesses anti-microbial activity through the activation of (NADPH) oxidase system and the subsequent production of reactive oxygen species.

M2 macrophages metabolize arginine using the arginase pathway, which is stimulated by cytokines such as IL-4, IL-6, IL-10, and IL-13. As the cytokines indicate, the arginase pathway in macrophages arginase, yielding ornithine and urea. As Ornithine metabolized into proline and polyamines, through a metabolic pathway. Proline is essential for collagen synthesis, while polyamines mediate

diverse functions such as gene expression, translation, cell proliferation, cell growth, cell signalling.... Arginase competes with NOSs for the common endogenous substrate L-arginine, preventing the overproduction of NO and associated tissue damage during prolonged inflammation. Because excess NO cause inhibition of cell proliferation and tissue injury.

E. Effects on Disease Condition

1. Coccidiosis

Etiology: *E. Tenella*, *E. Necatrix*

- Arginine increases the synthesis of polyamines requires for mucosal tissue repair and Nitric oxide (NO) destroying pathogenic micro-organism and restrict their multiplication.

2. Necrotic enteritis

Etiology: *C. Perfringens*

- Arginine improves the **intestinal absorption capacity** by improving villus height, protects the integrity of mucosal membranes of the GIT, and also increases the **population of the beneficial gut microbiome**.
- Preventing the spread of micro-organisms

3. Infectious bursal disease

Etiology: *Infectious Bursal Disease Virus (IBDV)*

- Arginine prevents immunosuppression and enhances the effectiveness of vaccine
- Its stimulate action on different cell types like T and B cells, natural killer (NK) cells, lymphokine-activated killer cells, and macrophages.

- Increased the antibody titers and it can help in the differentiation of pro-B to pre-B cells.

Overall benefits of arginine supplementation

Commercial product

- JOLLYBOY NUTRITION PRIVATE LIMITED at 350 Rs/kg
- Best amino contain 25 kg arginine preparation at 750 Rs/kg
- ADELBERT contain 25 kg arginine at 450 Rs/kg

CONCLUSIONS

- Arginine is a precursor of important metabolic components such as Nitric oxide (NO), glutamate, polyamines, and proline
- Arginine improves feed intake, body weight gain and FCR in various level of arginine supplements above the NRC recommendation
- Arginine improves antibody titer against NDV and IBD virus. Its shows higher concentration of plasma nitric oxide production that destroys pathogenic micro-organism
- Arginine reduces abdominal fat by lower activity of FAS enzyme and

higher activity of CPT 1 enzyme activity and higher carcass weight

- Arginine supplementation shows the protective function in both gross and histopathological conditions of intestine

FUTURE PROSPECTS

- Future research is essential to determine optimal arginine level with its economics
- Understanding arginine's influence on gut microbiota and disease resistance could revolutionize poultry nutrition strategies

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